

As on 20-01-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended for recording the crops alternative names knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to find several sources mentioning of the crops. The sources may be review papers, databases and web articles. Data is search by using the scientific name of the crop to ensure the right crop is taken.
2. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

1. Prior to data entry, one should know the following:
 - **'Alternative Names'** is the main table for recording the alternative names and location where the alternative names are used.
 - Procedures of data entry into the database (how to enter the data into the table); user will be trained for the data entry before entering data.
2. **IMPORTANT:** Prior to data entry, one has to ensure that the crop data that is going to be entered does not exist in record of the database.
3. There are five fields to be entered, four of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

3.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the common name which belongs to a specific crop subspecies, variety, cultivar or landrace.

3.2 Location (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the location where the alternative names of a specific crop that will be entered is commonly used.
- For one location, it is not limited to one alternative name only. Same location can be used for other alternative name.
- Select 'Global' if there is no specific location is stated.

3.3 Alternative Name (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the other alternative binomial name given to a specific crop species, subspecies, variety, cultivar or landrace that are used in different locations.
- One usually could find the alternative name by searching using the whole name of an organism's scientific name.
- The alternative name must be **UNIQUE** to other records. Ensure there is **NO** redundant data in previous records before creating a new record.

3.4 Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the alternative name of a specific crop itself.

3.5 Metadata ID (Compulsory)

- This field is to link the record to the metadata of alternative names.
- One MUST create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.